

THIS LAND IS NOT MINE

This Land is Not Mine focusses on the region of Lusatia, where Germany, Poland and the Czech Republic meet, the home of the Sorbian ethnic group. This new media project explores identity in a region of co-existing cultures that is undergoing fundamental socio-economic changes as brown coal mining in the region is phased out.

The work will be presented as a series of sound compositions and video connecting the changing identity of the region and sustainable transitions. Field recordings of the mines and surrounding areas and sounds of the chemistry of the water in the region (using the artist's specially developed instruments) will be combined with sounds gathered from the region's community members that characterise their own identity, and through discussions around the way in which the region is changing. The artwork, and the collaborative processes that generate it, will foment change towards sustainability by probing the roots of the region's identity, thereby sparking new conversations and possibilities about Lusatia's future.

This Land is Not Mine focusses on how identity plays a role in shaping the sustainability of the region in the future, with a particular focus on integrating Sorbian identity in a coherent narrative for the region's population. Sustainability requires not only this stepping away from coal and innovation, but also to connect with less tangible resources already present, such as culture, experience and tradition.

Previous related work

THE MATTER OF THE SOUL

The **Matter of the Soul** is a musical and sono-sculptural work exploring human empathy with the process of dispersal in the Arctic. Musical compositions include sounds from instruments made from hacked scientific equipment that measure chemical properties of water. Austen plays Arctic water live using these instruments during performances.

[More information](#)

Credits

Research for *The Matter of the Soul* was carried out during the Artist in the Arctic residency 2017 with Friends of Scott Polar Research Institute. During a residency on the ship the Akademik Sergei Vavilov, sailing through the Canadian High Arctic, Austen made field recordings of the acidity and salinity of Arctic waters using hacked pH and conductivity meters, and conducted interviews. Scientific instruments were donated by the teaching laboratories of the Chemistry Department, UCL. The work was further developed during Austen's Cultural Fellowship in Art and Science at the University of Leeds' Cultural Institute, with additional support from Ice Alive and the Polar Museum.

About Kat Austen

Kat Austen is a person. In her artistic practice, she focusses on environmental issues. She melds disciplines and media, creating sculptural and new media installations, performances and participatory work. Austen's practice is underpinned by extensive research and theory, and driven by a motivation to explore how to move towards a more socially and environmentally just future.

Working from her studio in Berlin, Austen is currently Artist in Residence at WRO Art Center through the EMAP/EMARE programme, Artistic Fellow at IASS Potsdam, Associate at ZeM, Brandenburg, Artist in Residence at the Faculty of Maths and Physical Sciences, University College London and Senior Teaching Fellow at UCL Arts and Sciences. She is a Fellow of the Royal Society of Arts, a member of the bbk, an inaugural member of the London Creative Network and is co-founder of the DIY Hack the Panke collective in Berlin

Austen's field research has included a voyage around the Canadian High Arctic as Artist in the Arctic 2017 for Friends of Scott Polar Research Institute (University of Cambridge) for her project The Matter of the Soul. In 2018 Austen was selected as inaugural Cultural Fellow in Art and Science at the Cultural Institute, University of Leeds for the same project. Austen has been awarded residencies internationally, including with NYU Shanghai, ArtOxygen Mumbai, LAs theatre, the Clipperton Project and Utter! Spoken word.

Austen has exhibited at Bonhams Art Gallery, London; The Polar Museum, Cambridge; Kuehlhaus, Berlin, among others, and her work is held internationally in private collections. She has performed around the globe, including at Opera North, Leeds; Fusion Festival, Berlin and Headlands Center for the Arts, San Francisco.

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